

THE MOTIVATIONAL DYNAMICS OF EFL TEACHERS: GOAL-SETTING, INTRINSIC INTEREST, AND TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract:

The prominence of teacher motivation in teaching practices and behaviors and its impact on student achievement is widely recognized in educational psychology. Nevertheless, English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers' motivation and the factors influencing its development appear an uncharted domain. The following study attempted to explore EFL teachers' motivation in relation to intrinsic interest, goal setting, and teaching effectiveness. The sample comprised 127 Iranian EFL teachers with their students (N= 500). The teachers were asked to complete a battery of two questionnaires. To assess teacher goal-setting and intrinsic interest, the researcher utilized the '*Teacher Self-Regulation Scale (TSRS)*' designed by Yesim, Sungur, and Uzuntiryaki (2009). To gauge teacher motivation, '*The Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers*' designed by Fernet (2009) was employed. In the present study, this questionnaire was translated to Persian and then the translated version was validated in the Iranian context to pave the way for future studies on teacher motivation in Iranian context. To measure language teachers' performance and success in language teaching, the researcher employed the '*Characteristics of Successful Iranian EFL Teachers Questionnaire*' (CSIET) designed and validated by Moafian and Pishghadam (2009). The results of structural equation modeling (SEM) indicated that there were relatively strong interrelationships among the three variables (intrinsic interest, goal-setting, and job motivation). All of them were positive and significant predictors of teacher success, and intrinsic interest exhibited the highest impact. It was also found that intrinsic

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interest positively influenced job motivation. The SEM analysis also indicated that goal-setting was positively influenced by both intrinsic interest and job motivation.

Keywords: teacher motivation, intrinsic interest, goal-setting, teacher success, SEM analysis

1. Introduction

Motivation is defined as the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behaviors. Motivation is what causes us to act, whether it is getting a glass of water to reduce thirst or reading a book to gain knowledge (Ushioda, 2003). It involves the biological, emotional, social, and cognitive forces that activate behavior (Dornyei, 2005). In everyday usage, the term *motivation* is frequently used to describe *why* a person does something. Motivation is the key to all learning. Lack of motivation is perhaps the biggest obstacle faced by teachers, counselors, school administrators, and parents. Behavioral problems in the classroom often, or always, seem to be linked to the lack of motivation. Teachers are among the most important factors contributing to motivation for learning. Ushioda (2003) argued that teachers, just like learners, want group development processes, opportunities for continuing individual learning, dialogic interaction with others, common goals, freedom to experiment, value as a member of the group, and appropriate levels of work and responsibility. These are all factors that a good work environment offers the teacher, and it is these significant factors that help to provide teachers with the necessary motivation to work and do their jobs effectively. Such traits as passion, interest, inspiration, drive, and dedication are arguably necessary qualities in most motivated people. However, one must realize that "*only arousing interest is not enough to be motivated*" (Williams & Burden, 1997, p.111). Teachers that are motivated will work harder, put more effort into trying new techniques and activities, and in general do more for the sake of the students, all of which contribute to smoother classes and more efficient learning. Despite the mounting evidence that enthusiasm and motivation strongly influence ways of understanding and acting in the classroom setting, little attention has been paid to teacher motivation.

The significance of teacher motivation is more evident when it comes to language learning in countries like Iran where English is mainly used in English institutes and is mostly instructed by classroom teachers. Effective teaching leads to effective learning, which is the ultimate goal of English classes. Teachers are one of the most influential elements for the success of any educational system.

During the last 50 years, many researchers and professionals, being responsible for teacher development and evaluation, have sought to establish criteria for assessing effective teaching. Many factors can suffice to create a context for good teaching, but it is teachers themselves who ultimately determine the success of a program. Good teachers can often make up for deficiencies in the curriculum, the materials, or the resources they make use of in their teaching (Richards, 2001). Good and qualified teachers are essential for efficient functioning of educational systems and for enhancing the quality of learning. Teachers also have a fundamental role in their learners' academic achievement and motivation (Campbell, Kyriakides, Muijse, & Robinson, 2004). Teachers' personal and psychological factors are the decisive elements affecting their teaching and learning. More specifically, teacher' motivation and teacher' self-regulation are among the factors which have crucial impact on teachers' orientation toward the educational process and their effective teaching (Ghonsooly & Ghanizadeh, 2013; Ghanizadeh & Royaei, 2015).

As Cardelle-Elawar, Irwin, and Lizarraga (2007) maintained successful teachers are self-regulated individuals who perceive themselves as teachers and sustain their motivation encountering different tasks, diverse students, and changing circumstances. Furthermore, self-regulation can help teachers gain a better understanding of their students' needs and learning experiences, have a deeper sense of the teaching and learning strategies, and emulate for the students (Paris & Winograd, 2001). Two outstanding subcategories of self-regulation of teachers are '*intrinsic interest*' and '*goal setting*'. Goal setting is defined as process of establishing objectives to guide actions during instruction (Yesim, Sungur, & Uzuntiryaki, 2009). A goal is what the individual is trying to accomplish, the object or aim of an action (Lock, Shaw, Sarri, & Latham, 1981). In setting goals, the established goals become the parameters that direct the attention of teachers on what is happening in a classroom (Ghanizadeh & Ghonsooly, 2014). It is important that teachers have some framework to use in thinking about what kinds of goals would be more worthwhile (McGreal, 1980). Intrinsic interest is defined as beliefs concerning personal interest in the profession (Yesim, Sungur, & Uzuntiryaki, 2009). It is contended in this study that teachers who are interested in their jobs would be more successful in their profession.

2. Purpose and Significance of the Study

As we know, goals or objectives are of prime importance in educational contexts since they are considered as underlying reasons for motivation (Wiggins & McTighe, 2000). Goals are fundamental elements of motivation and learning (Schunk, 2003). Goal setting

and intrinsic interest are two component of self-regulation which are very decisive in effectiveness (Yesim, Sungur, & Uzuntiryaki, 2009). However, there is a scarcity of research on the influence of goal-setting and intrinsic interest on teaching effectiveness. The necessity for such a study is seriously felt when one realizes that such study can provide the experts in the field of language teaching with information about the pivotal role of goal-setting and intrinsic interest theory in successful teaching. The present study is a partial attempt to fill this gap. More precisely, this study aims to focus particularly on the interrelationship between Iranian EFL teachers' motivation, goal-setting, and intrinsic interest in accounting for teaching effectiveness. The findings are expected to pave the way for proposing a model for EFL teacher effectiveness. To this end, the following research questions were posed and investigated in this study:

1. Does Iranian EFL teachers' intrinsic interest have any significant impact on teaching effectiveness?
2. Does Iranian EFL teachers' goal-setting have any significant impact on teaching effectiveness?
3. Does Iranian EFL teachers' job motivation have any significant impact in teaching effectiveness?

3. Method

3.1 Participants

A sample of convenience was used for this study. The population sample consisted of Iranian EFL teachers who were teaching English in several private institutes in Mashhad, a city in the north-east of Iran between November and January 2015. The research was carried out in these institutes, Iran National language institution, Parax Institue, Rashed Institue.

There were no requirements other than that the participants be currently teaching an English course during the fall semester of 2015. The target number of teachers for the study was 127. They were between 22 to 40 years old with 1 to 15 years of teaching experience. Out of 127 teachers, 79 were females and 48 were males. The majority of participants had majored in different branches of English, i.e., English teaching, English literature, English translation and those teachers who had certificate in majors except English were qualified to teach it.

The second group of participants comprised 500 EFL learners (students of the above-mentioned teachers). They were between 15 to 40 years old. Participants had different major and majority of them were university students.

3.2 Instruments

3.2.1 Teacher Self-Regulation Scale (TSRS)

To assess teacher goal-setting and intrinsic interest, the researcher utilized the 'Teacher Self-Regulation Scale (TSRS)' designed and validated by Yesim, Sungur, and Uzuntiryaki (2009).

It was developed based on Zimmerman's self-regulation model and consists of 11 items on a 6 point Likert scale ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. [strongly agree with the explanation (6), agree (5), slightly agree (4), slightly disagree (3), disagree (2) or strongly disagree (1)] according to their own opinions, insights, and understanding of the reason of each situation. Goal-setting is defined as process of establishing objectives to guide actions during instruction. And intrinsic interest is defined as beliefs concerning personal interest in the profession.

Sample item for goal-setting are as follows:

1. While preparing classes, I identify goals to be achieved by students.
2. While preparing classes, I decide on the instructional strategy appropriate for the topic.
3. While preparing classes, I take student characteristics (e.g. Prior knowledge, developmental level) into consideration.

Sample items for intrinsic interest are as follows:

1. It makes me happy to see my students learn.
2. I am proud of working as a teacher.
3. I have been interested in teaching profession since my childhood

3.2.2 Characteristics of Successful Iranian EFL Teachers Questionnaire

To evaluate language teachers' performance and success in language teaching, the researcher employed the 'Characteristics of Successful Iranian EFL Teachers Questionnaire' (CSIET) (Moafian & Pishghadam, 2009). It is a Likert scale consisting of 47 items and measuring twelve constructs as *Teaching accountability, Interpersonal relationships, Attention to all, Examination, Commitment, Learning boosters, Creating a sense of competence, Teaching boosters, Physical and emotional acceptance, Empathy, Class attendance, Dynamism*. This questionnaire was filled up by the students of the above teachers.

The sample items of the scale are as follows:

My teacher

1. Has a good knowledge of subject matter.
2. Has up to date information.
3. Is interested in the subject matter he/she is teaching.

4. Is aware of new teaching methods and strategies.
5. Has the subject matter well-organized according to the number of sessions and hours.

3.2.3 Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire

To the researcher's best knowledge, the only validated and documented questionnaire for measuring teacher motivation was constructed by Fernet (2008). In this study, this questionnaire was first translated to Persian and then the translated version was validated in Iranian context to pave the way for future studies on teacher motivation in Iranian context. It is a Likert scale consisting of 15 items measuring five constructs as *Intrinsic Motivation, Identified Regulation, Introjected Regulation, External Regulation, External Regulation*.

Sample items of the scale are listed in the followings:

I selected this job because

1. Because it is pleasant to carry out this task. (intrinsic motivation)
2. Because it is pleasant to carry out this task. (identified regulation)
3. Because if I don't carry out this task, I will feel bad. (introjected regulation)
4. Because the school obliges me to do it. (external regulation)
5. I used to know why I was doing this task, but I don't see the reason anymore. (amotivation)

4. Data Collection and Procedure

The study was conducted in several private Language Institutes in Mashhad, a city in North-east of Iran, between November and January 2015. The Institutes were selected based on convenience sampling. The teachers were distributed TSRS and (WTMST) questionnaires which they completed and delivered back to the researcher. Simultaneously, the CSIET questionnaire was given to the learners of those teachers. Through this questionnaire, the teachers' performance was evaluated by their students. To receive the reliable evaluation by the learners, the researcher explained the purpose of completing the questionnaire and assure the learners that their views were confidential; besides, both teachers and learners' questionnaires were coded numerically and they were asked not to write any name on their questionnaires. They were required to provide demographic information such as, gender, age, teaching experience, years of studying English and major.

4.1 Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data in this study the responses that were obtained from the questionnaires were tabulated and analyzed using SPSS software. A structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis was performed to examine the cause-effect relationship between teacher motivation, intrinsic interest, goal-setting, and teacher success. SEM is broadly utilized in the social sciences because of its ability to isolate observational error from measurement of latent variables (Schreiber et al., 2006). It most commonly refers to a combination of two things: a "measurement model" that defines latent variables using one or more observed variables, and a "structural regression model" that links latent variables together (Kaplan, 2007; Kline, 2011). To examine the structural relations, the proposed model was tested using the LISREL 8.50 statistical package.

Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were used to summarize the data. Means and standard deviations were computed for the constructs of EFL teachers' intrinsic interest, goal-setting, job motivation, and success. A number of fit indices were examined to evaluate the model fit: the chi-square magnitude which shouldn't be significant, Chi-square/*df* ratio which should be lower than 2 or 3, the normed fit index (NFI), the good fit index (GFI), and the comparative fit index (CFI) with the cut value greater than .90, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of about .06 or .07 (Schreiber et al., 2006). To check the strengths of the causal relationships among the variables, the *t*-values and standardized estimates were examined. The correlation coefficients were calculated among EFL teachers' intrinsic interest, goal-setting, job motivation, and success.

5. Results

Table 1 summarizes the result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to check the normality of data distribution. As it can be seen, the obtained sig value for all variables is higher than .05. Therefore, it can safely be concluded that the data is normally distributed across all four variables.

Table 1: The Results of K-S Test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Intrinsic interest	.091	127	.061*
Goal-setting	.086	127	.065*
Job motivation	.063	127	.200*
Teacher success	.092	127	.062*

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics of EFL teachers' intrinsic interest, goal-setting, job motivation, and success.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Intrinsic Interest, Goal-Setting, Job Motivation, and Success

	N	Possible range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Goal-setting	127	6-36	20.00	35.00	27.1496	4.26704
Intrinsic Interest	127	6-30	10.00	31.00	22.4724	5.34942
Job Motivation	127	15-75	30.00	71.00	53.1890	9.14672
Success	127	47-235	117.00	291.00	202.3307	29.36796
Valid N (listwise)	127					

As the Table indicates, the mean score of goal-setting is 27 out of 36. The mean score of intrinsic interest is 22 out of 30. For job motivation, the mean is 53 out of 75, and for teacher success, it is 202 out of 235.

5.1 The Results of CFA for Determining the Validity of Job Motivation Scale for Teachers

To determine the validity of the translated job motivation scale, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) using LISREL 8.5 was run. The model contained five subscales, each comprising three items as follows: *intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and motivation*. A number of fit indices were examined to evaluate the model fit: the chi-square magnitude which shouldn't be significant, Chi-square/df ratio which should be lower than 2 or 3, the normed fit index (NFI), the good fit index (GFI), and the comparative fit index (CFI) with the cut value greater than .90, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of about .06 or .07 (Schreiber, et al., 2006).

As demonstrated by Figure 1, the chi-square/df ratio (2.1), the RMSEA (.062), NFI=.90 all reached the acceptable fit thresholds. Overall, it can be concluded that the proposed model had a good fit with the empirical data.

To check the strengths of the causal relationships among the variables, the *t*-values and standardized estimates were examined. As indicated in Figure 1, two estimates were displayed on the paths. The first one is the standardized coefficient (β) which explains the predictive power of the independent variable and presents an easily grasped picture of effect size. The closer the magnitude to 1.0, the higher the correlation and the greater the predictive power of the variable is. The second measure is the *t*-

value (t); if $t > 2$ or $t < -2$, we call the result statistically significant. As the figure demonstrates, all items had accepted factor loadings.

$\chi^2=718.22$, $df=346$, $RMSEA=.071$, $CFI=.90$, $GFI=.88$, $NFI=.86$

Figure 1: The schematic representation of the five subscales of teacher motivation

The Cronbach's alpha estimate for the scale was found to be .91 regarding 25 items. The reliability of the subscales ranged from .81 to .89.

5.2 The Results of the Relationship between the Variables under the Study

To examine the structural relations, the proposed model was tested the LISREL 8.50 statistical package. As stated earlier, A number of fit indices were examined to evaluate the model fit: the chi-square magnitude which shouldn't be significant, Chi-square/ df

ratio which should be lower than 2 or 3, the normed fit index (NFI), the good fit index (GFI), and the comparative fit index (CFI) with the cut value greater than .90, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of about .06 or .07 (Schreiber, et al., 2006).

As demonstrated by Figure 2, the chi-square value (0.00), the chi-square/*df* ratio (0.00), the RMSEA (0.00), the GFI (1.00), the CFI (1.00), and the NFI (1.00) all reached the acceptable fit thresholds. In other words, the model has a **perfect** fit with the empirical data.

$\chi^2 = 0.00$, $df = 0$, $P\text{-value} = 1.00$, $RMSEA = 0.00$, $GFI = 1.00$, $NFI = 1.00$, $CFI = 1.00$

Figure 2: The schematic representation of the relationships among intrinsic interest, goal-setting, job motivation, and success

To check the strengths of the causal relationships among the variables, the *t*-values and standardized estimates were examined. The results demonstrated that three variables (intrinsic interest, goal-setting, and job motivation) are all positive and significant predictors of teacher success with intrinsic interest having the highest impact: goal setting ($\beta = .59$, $t = 9.14$), intrinsic interest ($\beta = .51$, $t = 8.42$), and job motivation ($\beta = .48$, $t = 6.01$). It was also found that intrinsic interest positively influenced job motivation ($\beta =$

.58, $t = 9.04$). Goal-setting was positively influenced by both intrinsic interest ($\beta = .59$, $t = 9.14$) and job motivation ($\beta = .49$, $t = 5.86$).

Table 3: The Correlation Coefficients among EFL Teachers' Intrinsic Interest, Goal-Setting, Job Motivation, and Success

	1	2	3	4
1. Intrinsic interest	1.00			
2. Goal-setting	.718**	1.00		
3. Job motivation	.649**	.632**	1.00	
4. Teacher success	.732**	.505**	.630**	1.00

**Correlation is significant at the level of 0.05

As it can be seen, in line with the results of path analysis, teacher success has the highest correlation with intrinsic interest ($r = 0.732$, $p < 0.05$) followed by job motivation ($r = 0.630$, $p < 0.05$) and goal-setting ($r = 0.505$, $p < 0.05$). It was also found that job motivation correlated positively and strongly with intrinsic interest ($r = 0.649$, $p < 0.05$) and goal-setting ($r = 0.632$, $p < 0.05$). Goal-setting was found to be highly positively associated with intrinsic interest ($r = 0.718$, $p < 0.05$).

6. Discussion

The current study sought to explore the role of EFL teachers' motivation, and two components of self-regulation (intrinsic interest and goal-setting) in their teaching effectiveness. In this section, responses extracted from data analysis have been presented in a way that elaborately addresses the research questions posed in this study:

A. Discussion of the First Research Question

Considering the first research question which asked whether Iranian EFL teachers' intrinsic interest have any significant role in teaching effectiveness (as measured by 'Teacher Self-Regulation Scale'), the results of the present study revealed that there was a significant relationship between these variables.

This finding suggests that teachers who are intrinsically interested performed better in their professions. This can plausibly be interpreted from the commonsense perspective, given that individual who have higher levels of intrinsic interest in their profession are expected to exhibit more persistence, commitment, and effort investment. This in turn would result in the successful accomplishment of their professional tasks. Current research has also confirmed that teachers' high academic

sense of intrinsic interest is a useful predictor of their job performance (Bembenutty, 2007).

In line with this study, prospective teachers should be equipped with self-regulatory strategies so as to be able to teach these skills and model for their students, since it seems plausible to presume that teachers who lack self-regulatory skills will find it difficult or even impossible to construct the self-regulation of their students. Furthermore, the contributing effects of intrinsic and emotional factors on teaching, especially those targeted at improving teaching task and personal interest, should be taken into account by the EFL trainers and teachers themselves (Ghanizadeh & Royaei, 2015).

Accordingly, teacher educators are recommended to incorporate emotional literacy programs to the agenda of teacher training programs. It is also important to appraise teachers' performance with reference to their prior achievements or their efforts rather than in comparison with other teachers (Monshi Toussi, & Ghanizadeh, 2012).

B. Discussion of the Second Research Question

The second question aimed at investigating the relationship between Iranian EFL teachers' goal-setting in teaching effectiveness. The results demonstrated a significant relationship between the variables in question. In another words, teachers' success as evaluated by their students was positively influenced by their goal-setting

A goal is what the individual is trying to accomplish, the object or aim of an action (Lock, Shaw, Saari, & Latham, 1981). Goal-setting is a fundamental element of social learning theory (Bandura, 1977). Goals encourage people to invest much effort and show persistence, and they make people concentrate their attention on relevant task features and the strategies which facilitate their succeeding in the task (Locke & Latham, 1990).

Goal-setting theory states that the process of setting goals and targets allows one to be focused and provides one with a sense of direction which enables one to achieve one's aims/objectives without distractions. It also builds self-confidence and improves performance as one recognizes the ability and competence in achieving set goals. Goals represent concretized or focused needs. In other words, if one intends to do something, there is the need to plan how to do it. According to Locke and Latham (1990), two conditions must be met before goals can positively influence self-efficacy and performance. First, the individual must be aware of the goal and its objectives. Second, the individual must accept the goal as something he or she is willing to work for. This theory is relevant to the study as it clarifies the issue that self-set goals would produce

high self-efficacy and better self-regulated performance than assigned goals. Teachers are likely to be committed to attaining their goals and feel efficacious about doing so thereby enhancing self-efficacy and self-regulation.

To improve competence in teaching and master the teaching task against self-set standards, as Yesim, Sungur, and Uzuntiryaki (2009), –teachers should be attentive to setting goals and persisting in observing these goals to enhance their teaching effectiveness. The above findings are in line with empirical and theoretical contentions highlighting the positive role of teachers' intrinsic interest and goal setting two components of self-regulatory skills in successful accomplishment of their professional tasks. According to Delfino, Dettori, and Persico (2010), the complexity of the individual and social aspects of teaching roles calls for self-regulated teachers who can manifest teaching effectiveness. Indeed, as Randi (2004) maintained from social cognitive perspective, effective teachers are self-regulated agents who can activate their beliefs to take appropriate actions leading to successful and effective teaching. In a similar vein, Dembo (2001) argued that to create opportunities for insightful instruction, teachers not only need content area knowledge, but also have to scrutinize their self-regulatory factors associated with teaching and learning. The abovementioned studies were all conducted in L1 contexts. The findings of the present study substantiated the positive role of two components of teacher self-regulation in their pedagogical success among Iranian EFL teachers. This is to some extent in accordance with a number of recent research studies among EFL teachers which demonstrated that teacher self-regulation is highly associated with teacher self-efficacy and effectiveness (Ghonsooly & Ghanizadeh, 2013; Monshi Toussi, & Ghanizadeh, 2012).

C. Discussion of the Third Research Question

The results of the third research question substantiated the contribution of teacher motivation to their pedagogical success. Teachers who have a high level of motivation work efficiently and effectively and it is of great importance for teachers in terms of their job satisfaction and job performance. In addition, a high level of job motivation of teachers can have a positive impact on the achievements of students. If the teachers are satisfied and motivated, then they are to greater extent committed and involved to their job. Teachers must be motivated well enough to perform well in their jobs. Otherwise, it will be impossible for them to be effective in teaching. Providing suitable psychological states in schools will help to enhance high work motivation and work satisfaction.

Finally, by investigating and understanding what it is that motivates teachers, we can improve teacher motivation and student learning. Teachers who are motivated will be more likely to work hard and spend more time refining their skills, thus better

managing their students, leading to better learning and having a positive impact on the learning environment. This paper will hopefully inspire language teachers to reflect on their own motivations and thereby bring about positive change for both themselves and the language students in an improved classroom environment.

7. Conclusions

The information derived from this study can have important implications in teacher education domain. To improve teacher's motivation, we have to consider these factors such as: income status, importance in the society, self-confidence, incentives and rewards on showing good results.

It is also recommended that no teachers be appointed without a professional training in education and in service; courses should be arranged for the teachers at regular intervals of time. It will update the teachers in the contents of the related subjects as well as in the area of teaching skills.

It is proposed that self-regulatory enhancing courses be designed and implemented for the purpose of teacher education and that these courses be conducted at the time of teacher selection both for the pre-service teacher training and for the appointment of teachers. This will identify positive attitudes of teachers towards teaching profession.

Teachers are the backbone of the educational institutes and future of our nation lies in their hands. In order to improve the quality of education, there is a need to spend time and energy on teacher training, which in return may provide quality education. As contended by Kazeem (1999), teachers and other school worker tend to remain contented and reasonably motivated as long as salaries are paid on time and they are promoted regularly. Earlier, Eton (1984) identified the payment of salaries, allowances and promotion as the key factors that shape teacher's attitude towards their work.

As a direct implication of these aforementioned findings, it is arguably true that prompt payment of salaries induce a direct commitment to teaching. However, there is no *wide spread* agreement on the extent to which financial inducement motivate teachers. So this reason leads us to infer that prompt payment of salaries; allowances, and promotion are desirable incentives to boost teachers' motivation. It is generally believed that good salaries and their prompt payment are important motivating factors. Nevertheless, there is evidence that other factors can undermine the commitment to the job.

One of such factors is the disparity that exists between the teaching profession and other professions. For example, the working condition that surrounds the teaching

profession portrays the *face value* assigned to the profession. A typical example is the impoverished working environment teachers in the developing countries find themselves in. In such an environment, even if a teacher has an intrinsic motivation, at a short run, crisis associated to job satisfaction would adversely influence teacher motivation.

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